

Alternatives to rice monoculture in Bangladesh: The way of cleaner production and responsible consumption

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Abstract

Rice monoculture in Bangladesh affects the associated biodiversity. The study aimed to identify the alternatives to rice monoculture. Both primary and secondary data were used in this study. It was found that tubers notably potato, sweet potato, aroids, taro, yam and cassava cultivation can mitigate the negative impacts of the monoculture and ensure food security. In addition, crop diversification can improve soil health and control insects and pathogens. The study outlined a pathway of cleaner production for environmental sustainability and responsible consumption to minimize wastage.

Keywords: Rice monoculture, food security, cleaner production, responsible consumption, wastage

Introduction

The Gangetic Delta is famous for rice consumption since the Neolithic age (Muthukumaran, 2014). The Bangladeshis eat rice every day and at every meal (Rah *et al.* 2010). Most people start the day with a breakfast of '*Panta*' (boiled rice soaked overnight in water and slightly fermented). *Moori* (puffed rice), *Cheera* (flattened rice), '*Khoi*' (popped rice), '*Chal vaja*' (fried rice), '*Shirni*' (rice boiled with crude sugar and coconut milk) '*pitha*' (rice cake), '*khichuri*' (rice boiled with pulses), '*payesh* (rice boiled in milk plus sweet)' are very common in our everyday meals.

Bangladesh is an agriculture-based country having more than 163 million people living on 147570 sq km area of land (Ahmed *et al.* 2023). The population will be double in the next 40 years. The rice consumption is about 145 kg/year per person (Yunus *et al.* 2019), which is equal to 76% of the total calorie intake and 66% of the total protein requirement. The rice sector contributes one-half of the agricultural GDP and one-sixth of the national income in Bangladesh (Yunus *et al.* 2023). The total area under rice in Bangladesh is about 186,000 ha hectares with a production of 38.7 million tons (Rahman *et al.* 2023).

Impact of rice monoculture on the Environment

To grow more rice to feed more people, most of the cultivable lands were brought under rice production. Rice monoculture is the agricultural practice of producing rice over a field year after year. It causes quicker spread of diseases and pest outbreaks because a single crop is more susceptible to a specific pathogen or pest (Cui *et al.* 2023). It has negative impacts on agrobiodiversity. Rice monoculture provides a narrower range of habitat than crop diversification (Ge *et al.* 2023). The agricultural system consists of two dimensions of biodiversity: (1) the diversity of crops and animals chosen by a farmer for production (planned biodiversity) and (2), the "associated" biodiversity including the micro-organisms, insects, birds, and other wildlife so that both depend upon and help maintain agro-ecosystems. Monoculture affects the associated biodiversity. The abundance of beneficial insects like honeybees, bats, and birds tends to be lower in monocultures than in fields containing diverse forage and nesting sites (Liu *et al.* 2023). Continuous application of urea and other pesticides for rice monoculture has negative impacts on water quality, wildlife populations, and human health. Without integrated soil nutrient

management practices, soil fertility declines as the same crop absorbs nutrients from the same layer/ horizon of soils (Liu *et al.* 2023).

Methodology

Both primary and secondary data were used for this study. The secondary data were collected from different sources of literature. A focus group discussion was done incorporating the respondents from diverse stakeholders. A total number of 10 key informants were interviewed to identify the alternatives to rice monoculture and to find out the ways of ensuring cleaner production and responsible consumption. Content analysis was done to interpret the data.

Alternatives to rice monoculture

The respondents opined that crop diversification gives a wider choice in the production of a variety of crops in a given area to expand the production of various crops and also to reduce the risk. Crop diversification can be considered as a shift from traditionally grown less remunerative rice to more remunerative crops. Market and social attitudes are also related to inducing crop shifts. Higher profitability as well as the resilience/stability in production also induces crop diversification. Cultivation of a large number of crops in rainfed lands can reduce the risk factor of crop failures due to drought.

A slump in the market value for rice greatly reduces the income of the producers. Unfavourable weather or pest outbreak destroys a large part of the rice crop, leaving the farmer in ruins. Farmers having crop diversity can avoid these risks and provide their families with a healthy diet. The addition of more crops to the existing cropping system is termed horizontal diversification. The systems of multiple cropping can increase food production potential. In vertical crop diversification, various other downstream activities are undertaken. Malnutrition is still an issue of national urgency (Rahman 2021). The consumption of food items other than rice is much less than the minimum requirements. Further, the composition of the diet is not balanced as the lion's share of the calorie and protein intake comes from rice. Tuber crops can reduce malnutrition in Bangladesh.

In future, balanced use of land and water resources will be the central theme for the sustainability of agricultural growth in Bangladesh. There has been a growing concern in recent times about the deteriorating conditions of soil health and water resources due to the improper use of chemicals for rice monoculture. There is a greater need to have an integrated approach to the management of plant nutrients and chemicals. Tuber crop production may reduce this environmental degradation.

The crop that has a modified stem or root to store food materials is termed a tuber. They are rich in starch and can be used as a staple or a supplementary food in Bangladesh. Tuber crops like potato, sweet potato, aroid (*Kachu*), yam (*Meta alu/ Gachh alu*) and cassava (*Shimul alu*) grow in Bangladesh (Rahman et al. 2009, 2010). Tuber crops are cheaper sources of protein and calories and they also have a positive impact on the nutrient balance of the soil. The farmers can easily cultivate these crops after harvesting the major ones. Due to the 'Green Revolution' production of rice increased tremendously. But the production of tuber crops did not increase in the same trend. With this realization and to reduce the huge drain of foreign exchange in importing rice, tuber cultivation should be expanded throughout the country.

Potato

It can be considered as a security crop in times of rice shortages, due to its high carbohydrate content contributing to improved food security. It is also used as a vegetable by most people. As a short-duration crop, its increased use can reduce the pressure on rice. The average yield is triple of rice. Bangladesh can expand potato-cropped areas from the northwestern part to the middle part of the country. Potato - Boro (HYV) - T. Aman cropping pattern can ensure maximum return from a crop field.

Sweet potato

It is considered an important supplementary food as well as a poor people's food. Young stems and leaves are used as vegetables as well as fodder. The average yield is about triple of rice. It grows on marginal lands, homestead areas, roadsides and elsewhere as a low-input crop. Sweet potato- Aus- Fallow or Sweet Potato-Jute-Fallow cropping pattern can provide a maximum return from fallow land.

Aroids/ Taro (Kachu)

Most of the aroids are used as food, others are used as ornamentals and a few have medicinal value. It can grow on any land including moist and shady places. The average yield is more than double of rice. Taro (*Mukhi Kachu*), Giant Taro (*Man Kachu*), Elephant Foot Aroid (*Ol Kachu*), and Eddoe (*Pani Kachu*) are commercially cultivated in our country. The Arrow-leaf Elephant Ear (*Dudh Kachu*) and Tania (*Moulavi Kachu*) are mainly cultivated as vegetables. The leaves of some wild aroids are also edible. The aroids are rich in starch and can be processed like potatoes. Aroid starch is used to prepare baby foods for its easily digestible characteristic. It is a good quality source of minerals and vitamins. For its cultivation, no intercultural operations and

fertilizer or pesticide application are required. Its production should be encouraged to ensure maximum utilization of fallow or aquatic land.

Yams (Gachh alu/Meta alu)

Yams are a primarily agricultural and culturally important commodity in West Africa. They produce edible tubers, bulbils, or rhizomes. Yams naturally grow in the Sal/ Hill forests areas of Bangladesh but they are available all over the country. Purple yam (*Goichcha alu*), Air Yam (*Gachh alu*), Bitter Yam (*Bish alu*), Five-leaf Yam (*Jhum alu*), Cinnamon Yam (*Pesta alu*), Fancy Yam (*Machh alu*), Three-leaved Yam (*Shuori alu*), White Yam (*Sada alu*), Chinese Yam (*Chupri alu*), Yellow Guinea Yam (*Boroi alu*) and Ten-months Yam (*Mom alu*) are found in different parts of the country. It is cultivated mainly as a homestead plant and consumed as a vegetable. Like aroids, no intercultural operations and fertilizer or pesticide applications are required for their production. The average yield is triple of rice.

Cassava (Shimul alu)

It is a perennial shrub with enlarged tuberous roots resembling sweet potatoes and is eaten in the same way. In the Chittagong Hill Tracts and Garo Hill regions of the greater Mymensingh district, the *Adivasi* (tribal) people consume it as a supplementary staple. The average yield is a quintuple of rice. Like aroids and yams, no intercultural operations and fertilizer or pesticide applications are required for its production. Cassava is the highest calorie-productive crop from the same unit of land.

Responsible consumption and cleaner production of rice

By controlling a small portion of rice during cultivation, buying, cooking and eating we can reduce rice waste, save money and protect the environment.

Write a smart shopping list

The respondents suggested writing a smart shopping list consisting of 50% rice and 50% tubers for just your need.

Stick to the list

Don't be tempted by offers and don't buy when you are hungry, otherwise, you will come back with more rice than you need. Buy less quantity of rice than you need exactly: After buying more amounts of seasonal fruits and leafy vegetables, buy less amount of rice than you need exactly.

Cook /eat 50% rice + 50% tubers

Cook and eat 50% rice and 50% tubers (potato or sweet potato or yams or aroids or cassava) to satisfy your stomach. At first, you need to change your food habit slowly.

Don't throw cooked rice water (Fan/ Mar) away

Don't drain out cooked rice water as it is highly rich in amylose. Amylose is a water-soluble and easily digestible polysaccharide having an un-branched, linear, or spiral structure.

Rotate

Try to be habituated with new food items every day putting the older back. Eat less rice to flatten your belly: Eat clean but also observe your starches and sugars. Eat vegetables and cut the rice portion in half. This will start your system on the road to weight loss. Bulkiness makes you age and slimness makes you smart.

Serve small amounts

Serve a small quantity of rice with the understanding that everybody is not the same hungry. This is especially applicable to children, who rarely estimate how much they can eat at once. Any leftovers can be stored in the freezer for use another day or can be soaked overnight in water for taking as breakfast the next morning.

Use plant leaves on stored rice

Sustainable agriculture means productive agriculture that uses and conserves natural resources. We need to be proactive against the use of toxic chemicals. Foliages of some plant species having insecticidal properties can be used for storing rice without being toxic to pets and

humans. Dried leaves of Neem, Malabar Nut (*Basak*), Knotweed (*Bish kanthali*), Chaste Tree (*Nishinda*), Jimson Weed (*Datura*), Pennywort (*Thankuni Pata*), Bush Morning Glory (*Dhol Kolmi*), Onion, Garlic and Turmeric have repellent and lethal effects against the pests of rice. A five-centimetre-thick layer of dried leaves on the uppermost surface of the pots can protect the stored rice from the attack of any pest.

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